

ISic1208

Epitaph for Oltiskos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

cippus

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

From the area of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8702

Physical Description

A rectangular cippus of local sandstone, heavily damaged on the left, along the base, and the upper right corner.

Dimensions

Height 43 cm
Width 31.5 cm
Depth 14 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek letters, centred on the front face of the stone.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat, but irregularly sized letters. Omicron is smaller than the rest and mid-line; sigma is regular with horizontal top and bottom bars; kappa is tall with short arms, slightly curving out from the middle of the upright; alpha has straight bar (and in the second case is larger; epsilon has shorter middle bar.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 30-50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not recorded mm

Text

1. Ὀλίσκοϛ
2. Ἀριστέα

Apparatus

text of IG

Translation (en)

Oltiskos, son of Aristneas

Commentary

The name Ὀλτίσκος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%E1%BD%88%CE%BB%CF%84%CE%AF%CF%83%CE%BA%CE%BF%CF%82] is not otherwise attested. The patronymic, Ἀριστέας [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?lexname=nAriste1as], on the other hand is very common, and in Sicily is attested on the eastern side of the island (principally nearby Tauromenion, but also Syracuseae, Akrai, and Lipara). The use of the nominative for the deceased is less common on the inscribed epitaphs from Abakainon, but not unknown. Although dated on the grounds of letter forms to the C2-1 BC by Manni Piraino, the evidence from the necropolis suggests the range C3-2 BC is more plausible.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492812

EDR 147870

EDCS 39101572

PHI 140692

PHI 175727

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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